

4.16 AN ADVECTION-DIFFUSION SCHEME FOR THE CONVECTIVE
BOUNDARY LAYER:
DESCRIPTION AND 1D-RESULTS

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1 INTRODUCTION

There is an increasing call for a unified parameterisation of turbulent transport of heat and moisture in the cloud topped convective boundary layer. It is common practice to use an advective mass flux approach for the transport in the cumulus cloud layer and a diffusive approach for the transport in the subcloud layer and the dry boundary layer. These approaches have been developed quite independently and this Note should be viewed as a first step of coupling the two approaches on a physical sound base. All is based on the simple concept of a scale separation between large-scale organised strong updrafts and a remaining small-scale turbulent part. The organised, strongly skewed and non-local updraft part is described by an advective mass flux approach whereas the remaining symmetric small-scale turbulent part is described by a diffusive approach.

To become more specific let us arbitrarily define a strong updraft as a fixed fractional area a_u , say of a few percent of a large horizontal domain, that contains the strongest upward vertical velocities. Subsequently, we perform a breakdown of the turbulent flux of a field ϕ into three terms (Siebesma and Cuijpers, 1995)

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{w'\phi'} &= a_u \overline{w'\phi'^u} + (1 - a_u) \overline{w'\phi'^e} + M(\phi_c - \phi_e) \\ &\simeq (1 - a_u) \overline{w'\phi'^e} + M(\phi_u - \bar{\phi}) \\ &\simeq -K \frac{\partial \bar{\phi}}{\partial z} + M(\phi_u - \bar{\phi}) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where all notation is conventional: $M = a_u w_u$ is the mass flux of the strong updraft and the u and e subscripts refer to the updraft and the complementary environmental part. In the second step we use $a_u \ll 1$ so that the first term on the rhs can be neglected and $\phi_e \simeq \bar{\phi}$. In the last step we make the crucial assumption that we can approximate the symmetric complementary part by diffusion.

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In the remainder of this Note we will present a parameterization based on this simple approach for the dry convective boundary layer and compare its performance with LES results. We will also discuss its performance in relation to other more conventional parameterization schemes.

2 The Updraft Model

If we want to make a parameterization based on (1) we need a model for the potential temperature θ_u , specific humidity q_u and the vertical velocity w_u of these strong updrafts. To this purpose we use for $\phi = \{\theta, q\}$ a simple entraining plume model, similar the one used for cumulus convection (Betts, 1973)

$$\frac{\partial \phi_u}{\partial z} = -\varepsilon(\phi_u - \bar{\phi}) \quad (2)$$

where ε is the so-called fractional entrainment rate. We use a similar equation for the vertical velocity (Simpson and Wiggert, 1969)

$$w_c \frac{\partial w_c}{\partial z} = -\varepsilon w_c^2 + B \quad (3)$$

with a buoyancy term $B = g(\theta_v, u - \bar{\theta}_v) / \bar{\theta}_v$ as an extra source term.

The fractional entrainment rate ε we obtain from Large Eddy Simulation (LES) results based on a convective dry boundary layer case described in (Nieuwstadt et al., 1992). In close analogy with Van Ulden and Siebesma (1997) we simply define the strong updrafts as those grid points that contain the highest positive vertical velocities. In practice we take at each horizontal slab a constant fraction a_u of all the grid points that contain the strongest positive velocities. From this procedure we can "measure" the updraft fields ϕ_u in our numerical laboratory and subsequently use (2) to estimate the fractional entrainment rate. We tried different updraft fractions $a_u = 0.01, 0.02, \dots, 0.05$ but found that the diagnosed ε did not depend strongly on this choice. In fact we find that the ε obtained by LES can be well fitted by

$$\varepsilon \simeq c_\varepsilon \left(\frac{1}{z} + \frac{1}{z - z_i} \right) \quad (4)$$

where z_i is the inversion height and for the prefactor we find $c_\varepsilon \simeq 0.5$. A similar form has been proposed before based on observations (Van Ulden and Siebesma, 1997). The $\varepsilon \sim 1/z$ behavior near the surface has been reported recently also, based on LES results, for a simple updraft-downdraft decomposition (de Roode et al., 2000). We will therefore use (4) as a prescribed lateral entrainment rate in the updraft model.

We finally have to initialize the updraft model by taking the mean value at the lowest model level z_1 and adding an excess that scales with the surface flux (Troen and Mahrt, 1986)

$$\phi_u(z_1) = \bar{\phi}(z_1) + b \frac{\overline{w'\phi'_s}}{\sigma_w(z_1)} \quad (5)$$

where $\overline{w'\phi'_s}$ is the surface flux. The value of the prefactor b is again based on LES results and we use $b \simeq 1$. For the standard deviation σ_w we use an empirical expression based on a combination of atmospheric data, tank measurements and LES data (Holtslag and Moeng, 1991)

$$\frac{\sigma_w}{w_*} \simeq 1.2 \left(\left(\frac{u_*}{w_*} \right)^3 + 0.6 \frac{z}{z_i} \right)^{1/3} \left(1 - \frac{z}{z_i} \right)^{1/2} \quad (6)$$

where w_* is the usual convective velocity scale and u_* is the friction velocity.

The main new aspects of the present updraft model are twofold

- The updraft is mixing with the environment. Close to the surface where the entrainment rate has a $\varepsilon \sim 1/z$ behavior this has the great advantage that the precise choice of the initialization height z_1 becomes irrelevant. More precisely, if $\bar{\phi}$ has a logarithmic profile as is common in the surface layer one can show that for $\varepsilon \sim 1/z$ the excess $\phi_u - \bar{\phi}$ becomes height independent.
- The use of a vertical velocity equation. This equation is used to estimate z_i as the height where the w_u vanishes as opposed to simply take a zero buoyancy level as z_i . This way the overshoot of strong thermals into the inversion can be taken into account.

In conclusion, the updraft model calculates, given the surface fluxes and the mean profiles, the updraft fields θ_u, q_u and w_u and the inversion height z_i , the latter being the height where w_u vanishes.

3 The Advection-Diffusion Scheme

To complete the advection-diffusion scheme (1) we need to specify the eddy diffusivity K and the mass flux M . The most simplest and robust

method for the convective boundary layer is to use a profile method (Troen and Mahrt, 1986) and we will do so accordingly. A K-profile should at least

- obey surface layer similarity near $z = 0$
- vanish near the inversion
- have a peak value $K_{max}/(w_* z_i) \simeq 0.1$

Holtslag (1998) proposed the following K-profile K_h for heat and moisture that obey these conditions and that we will adopt here

$$K_h = k u_* \phi_{h0}^{-1} z \left(1 - \frac{z}{z_i} \right)^2 \quad (7)$$

with k the von Karman's constant and ϕ_{h0} an effective stability function given by

$$\phi_{h0} = \left(1 - 39 \frac{z}{L} \right)^{-1/3}, \quad (8)$$

where L is the Obukhov length.

Since the mass flux M scales well with the standard deviation σ_w we propose for the Mass flux M

$$M = c_m \sigma_w \quad (9)$$

with $c_m \simeq 0.5$.

The last step that remains to be done is to calculate the flux divergence as a result of both the diffusive and the advective part by employing a diffusion-advection solver

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \bar{\phi}}{\partial t} &= - \frac{\partial \overline{w'\phi'}}{\partial z} \\ &= - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(-K \frac{\partial \bar{\phi}}{\partial z} + M(\phi_u - \bar{\phi}) \right) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

For a discussion on the numerical aspects of this solver we refer to (Teixeira and Siebesma, 2000) elsewhere in these conference proceedings.

4 A CASE STUDY

As a simple case study we will use a dry convective pbl case which has been used for a LES inter-comparison study (Nieuwstadt et al., 1992). The initial θ -profile can be found in Fig.1. A sensible heat flux of $\overline{w'\theta'_s} = 6 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ K m/s}$ at the surface is prescribed. A typical moisture profile is added with a prescribed moisture surface flux which we will not show and discuss here.

A simple single column model (SCM) with the above prescribed advection-diffusion scheme has been coded. In order to exclude spatial discretization errors we use a high vertical resolution of 20 m. In Fig.1 we show the initial θ profile along with the mean profile calculated by the SCM after 7 hours of simulation. As a reference we also show the vertical profile produced by a LES run. From this we can conclude that the scheme produces a

correct pbl-growth. In Fig.2 we show the breakdown of the $\overline{w'\theta'}$ flux into the small-scale diffusive part and the advective mass flux part, i.e. the two terms on the rhs of (1). Note that the negative entrainment flux that determines the pbl-growth is largely determined by the mass flux term. Preliminary LES results confirm this picture that strong non-local updrafts are indeed largely responsible for the entrainment flux. Note that the advective mass flux can describe the entrainment flux since the excess $\theta_u - \bar{\theta}$ is changes in the inversion layer.

Figure 1: θ profiles after 7 hours of simulation for the advection-diffusion scheme.

Figure 2: Breakdown of the fluxes after 7 hours into a diffusive part and a mass flux part for the advection-diffusion scheme.

Let us finally confront this new scheme with the apparently closely related and widely used non-local approach Holtslag and Moeng (1991); Stevens (2000). Within that framework the turbulent flux is parameterized by

$$\overline{w'\phi'} = -K \frac{\partial \bar{\phi}}{\partial z} + K\gamma \quad (11)$$

where we take for the counter gradient term a formulation suggested by Cuijpers and Holtslag (1998)

$$\gamma = a \frac{w_*}{\sigma_w^2 z_i} \overline{w'\theta'_s} \quad (12)$$

with $a \simeq 2$. We have run the very same SCM with the same updraft model but now with the advective mass flux part replaced by the more conventional countergradient term such as given by (11) and (12). The SCM profile after 7 hours, (see Fig.3, illustrates that only little top-entrainment has taken place and that the pbl-height is consequently growing too slow. The reason for this can be understood if we make a similar breakdown into the two contributions of the rhs of (11) (see Fig.4). Because the non-local term is always positive (it cannot change sign as the mass flux term) it will always reduce the top-entrainment. In the present example K-diffusion and non-local term even balance so that there is hardly any top-entrainment. So including a counter gradient term has the effect of reducing the top-entrainment rate as compared with a similar formulation without a non-local term.

Figure 3: As in Fig.1 but now for the non-local formulation (11)

Figure 4: As in Fig.2 but now with the non-local formulation (11)

5 CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

We have shown that a simple combination of mass flux and diffusion can realistically describe the transport in the convective boundary layer. The main advantage of this avenue is that it naturally opens the way to a scheme for a cumulus topped boundary layer by allowing the strong updraft to condensate. No switching of a convection scheme is then necessary anymore. In that case the updraft model is always active and decides autonomically whether these updrafts becomes cloud core updrafts or not. Work in this direction is in full progress.

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